

SITE GPR	YEAR 10	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.7596 Max: 63.2105	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1181 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic		University of Michigan History Department of Anthropology Gabii Project
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 625-626	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION silty layer below tuffo layer (1180) in Room 1	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1180, 1158	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX															
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay 10% silt 90% sand ___%															
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae M <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Glass R	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) M <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clay R <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Silt F <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) R <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal R <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </table>		Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1180, 1158	Covers: 1204, 1205, 1306
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
Excavated with pick & trowel
 Δ188 - Miniaturizing Knives - shot in
 Δ184 - Bronze fish hook not shot in, general location indicated on sketch

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: South central
 Shape: Rectangular on sketch. See L and W measurements

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Surface is irregular throughout room
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Ceramic very frequent along western edge (wall SU 1183)
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

1184 = walls
 1184 - General location only

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Thick layer of silty soil used to form foundation for coccio pesto floor surface in Room 1. Although the floor surface and its gravel and crushed tufo preparation layers are truncated in much of the room, this silty layer seems to be intact throughout, below occupation surface.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by S. Roux

on 15.07.10

Revised by CHM

on 19.7.2010

PDFd by JSM

on 23.7.2010

Entered by

on